

Supplementary tables and figures of:

Cécilia Fontyn, Kevin JG Meyer, Anne-Lise Boixel, Ghislain Delestre, Emma Piaget, Corentin Picard, Frédéric Suffert, Thierry C Marcel, Henriette Goyeau (2023) Evolution within a given virulence phenotype (pathotype) is driven by changes in aggressiveness: a case study of French wheat leaf rust populations. *PCI Infections*, <https://doi.org/10.24072/pci.infections.100074>

Table S1. Number of isolates identified as pathotype 106 314 0 collected on 14 of the most frequently grown bread wheat cultivars during the 2006-2016 period and genotyped with 19 SSRs (see Table 3).

Cultivar	Registration year	Postulated resistance genes ^a	Year of sampling											Total	
			2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016		
Charger	1997	<i>Lr10, Lr13</i>	4												4
Tremie	1992	<i>Lr10, Lr13</i>	5												5
Sankara	2004	<i>Lr10, Lr13, Lr37</i>	4	5	3	5									17
Aubusson	2002	<i>Lr10, Lr13, Lr37</i>	5	5	3	5	3	5	5						31
Apache	1998	<i>Lr13, Lr37</i>	9	10	9	10	8	10	10	9	10				85
Orvantis	2000	<i>Lr10, Lr13, Lr37</i>		5											5
Soissons	1988	<i>Lr14a</i>		5	4	5									14
Mendel	2004	<i>Lr13</i>			3										3
Premio	2007	<i>Lr14a, Lr37</i>				5	4	5							14
Bermude	2007	<i>Lr10, Lr13, Lr14a, Lr37</i>					4	5	5	5		7			26
Arezzo	2008	<i>Lr10, Lr14a, Lr37</i>					4	5	5	5	5	8	1		33
Expert	2008	<i>Lr1, Lr13</i>								5	4	5		3	17
Pakito	2011	<i>Lr13, Lr37</i>									5	5	7		17
Solehio	2009	<i>Lr14a, Lr37</i>										5	7	3	15
Number of isolates			27	30	22	30	23	30	30	28	30	29	7	286	

^a *Lr* genes were postulated by performing multipathotype tests with standard isolates with known virulence genes (Fontyn *et al.*, 2022)

Table S2. Number of isolates identified as pathotype 166 317 0 collected on eight of the most frequently grown bread wheat cultivars during the 2013-2016 period and genotyped with 19 SSRs (see Table 3).

Cultivar	Registration year	Postulated resistance genes ^a	Year of Sampling				Total
			2013	2014	2015	2016	
Altigo	2007	<i>Lr3, Lr13, Lr37</i>	8				8
Bermude	2007	<i>Lr10, Lr13, Lr14a, Lr37</i>	5		5		10
Arezzo	2008	<i>Lr10, Lr14a, Lr37</i>	7	9	5	10	31
Pakito	2011	<i>Lr13, Lr37</i>	5	4	5		14
Solehio	2009	<i>Lr14a, Lr37</i>	5	5		5	15
Cellule	2011	<i>Lr3</i>		8	10	9	27
Apache	1998	<i>Lr13, Lr37</i>			5		5
Fructidor	2014	<i>Lr13, Lr14a</i>				5	5
Number of isolates			30	26	30	29	115

^a *Lr* genes were postulated by performing multipathotype tests with standard isolates with known virulences (Fontyn *et al.*, 2022)

Table S3. Experimental design for assessments of the aggressiveness of the two main genotypes (G1 and G2) of each of the two major pathotypes (106 314 0 and 166 317 0) of *Puccinia triticina* collected in France during 2005-2016: distribution of the isolates over five experimental series, cultivar from which the isolate was collected, and cultivars on which the aggressiveness of the isolate was assessed.

Isolate	Pathotype	Genotype	Series	Cultivar sampled	Cultivars tested
BT12M202	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M378	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M109	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M391	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M192	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M321	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M018	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M066	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M149	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M254	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M344	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT14M392	166 317 0	166 317 0-G1	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT16M219	166 317 0	166 317 0-G2	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT16M164	166 317 0	166 317 0-G2	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT16M246	166 317 0	166 317 0-G2	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT16M174	166 317 0	166 317 0-G2	2	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT05M021	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT05M241	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT05M067	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT06M138	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT06M195	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber

BT06M101	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT15M292	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT15M011	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT16V048	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT15M121	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT15M309	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT15M035	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1	Apache	Apache, Michigan Amber
BT12M380	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M355	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	3	Premio	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M137	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	3	Premio	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT13V142	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT13M108	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT13V026	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT13M168	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M281	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Aubusson	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M302	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Premio	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M379	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Premio	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M284	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	3	Premio	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber
BT12M119	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1+4	Apache	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber, Apache
BT12M033	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1+4	Apache	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber, Apache
BT13V137	106 314 0	106 314 0-G1	1+4+5	Apache	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber, Sankara, Expert, Bermude, Apache
BT13V189	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1+4+5	Apache	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber, Sankara, Expert, Bermude, Apache
BT12M326	106 314 0	106 314 0-G2	1+4+5	Apache	Aubusson, Premio, Michigan Amber, Sankara, Expert, Bermude, Apache

Table S4. Allocation of 19 SSR markers to two multiplexes, for genotyping *Puccinia triticina* isolates.

	SSR ID	Fluorescence label	Forward primer	Reverse primer	Chromosome position	Allele size range	Repeat size	Reference
Multiplex 1	RB8	Vic	CGCCGTTCCCATCGTTC	TAAACACTCCACCCACGCC	17A/17B	143-155	3	Duan et al., 2003
	PtSSR173	Vic	CTCAGCGACCTCAAAGAACC	GAGACGACGGATGTCAACAA	2A/2B	213-223	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR186	Vic	GCCACGAGAAATACATAGAAATAAAA	GGTTGTTGATGGGCTTGAGT	10A/10B	338-353	3	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	RB11	Pet	AGCAGTGAGCAGCAGCGTC	ACTACTGTGAGTGTCCGGCTTGG	-	175-206	2	Duan et al., 2003
	PtSSR158	6Fam	GACGACTTCGTCACTGCTGA	GAGGAGAAGCCGTTCTGTTG	3A/3B	226-238	3	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR68	Pet	GACTCAGCCCACTGCTAACC	GATGGCGACGTATTTGGTCT	9A/9B	309-341	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR50	6Fam	CATCGGAATGGTCTGTCTCC	CCAAATGCTATGAGTGGAAAA	12A/12B	365-373	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR164	Ned	GTGGAAGTGAGCGGAAGAAG	GGAGATGGGCAGATGAGGTA	10A/10B	219-233	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR61	Ned	CGAACTGGTACAACGCACTG	CGCAAAAAGGCTGATCTCTG	17A/17B	296-302	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
Multiplex 2	RB17	Vic	CTTCGGTAGGATTTGAGCG	CAGCTCCAAATCCTTTGCC	14A/14B	190-193	3	Duan et al., 2003
	PtSSR92	Pet	CCAAGGAACAGTCCACCAAG	GAGTCGGGTAAGCCATCTGA	1A/1B	246-258	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	RB12	Vic	CCACAAGCAACCACATACCACC	TGGTCCATGAAGAAGTCTCTGAAC	16A/16B	282-290	2	Duan et al., 2003
	RB26	Vic	TCGTCCTGCCTACCTCTGAC	AAAGTGCATGATCTGCATGTG	16A/16B	349-352	3	Duan et al., 2003
	PtSSR91	Ned	ATCTTGCGTCTCAGCCATCT	CGCCGCTCTTCATCTCTTAC	1A/1B	380-384	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR13	6Fam	CGAATTCGCGTTTTATGTCC	TGATCCAATCGAACCTAGCC	2A/2B	129-131	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	RB25	6Fam	ATGTCTGTAGTCGGCAGGGC	GCCTCTGCGGGATCGGT	4A/4B	228-230	2	Duan et al., 2003
	PtSSR55	6Fam	AGCTTACGGTCCTCAATCG	AGTGAAAGGGGCTGGGAGT	18A/18B	308-310	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR152	6Fam	CTCCGTTCTCTTTCTGTGCG	CCATCGCAACCAACAAACA	18A/18B	389-393	2	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007
	PtSSR154	Ned	ACGGTCAACAGCCAACCTACC	CCTCGTCATCCTGGTTGAGT	16A/16B	247-276	3	Szabo & Kolmer, 2007

Table S5. ANOVA *p-values* for series 1 and 2 testing whether the two genotypes (106 314 0-G1 and 106 314 0-G2 ; 166 317 0-G1 and 166 317 0-G2) within each *P. triticina* pathotype (106 314 0 and 166 317 0) differ in the aggressiveness components infection efficiency (IE), latency period (LP), and sporulation capacity (SP), on pooled data from cultivars Apache and Michigan.

Series	Pathotype	Component ¹	Source of variation							
			Repetition	df	Genotype	df	Cultivar	df	Isolate/Genotype	df
1	106 314 0	IE	<0.0001	2	0.9	1	0.1	1	<0.0001	15
		<u>LP</u>	<0.0001	2	0.7	1	<0.0001	1	0.2	15
		<u>SP</u>	<0.0001	2	0.05	1	0.03	1	<0.0001	15
2	166 317 0	<u>IE</u>	<0.0001	2	0.0001	1	0.0002	1	<0.0001	14
		<u>LP</u>	<0.0001	2	0.0003	1	<0.0001	1	0.01	14
		SP	0.003	2	0.01	1	0.004	1	0.0002	14

¹ An underlined component means that the data did not follow a normal distribution required for the ANOVA, however a non-parametric test (Kruskal-Wallis) gave the same results.

Table S6. ANOVA *p-values* for series 3, 4 and 5 testing whether the two genotypes 106 314 0-G1 and 106 314 0-G2 differ in the aggressiveness components infection efficiency (IE), latency period (LP), and sporulation capacity (SP), as assessed on Michigan and on five of the most widely grown cultivars in France during the 2005-2016 period.

Series	Tested cultivar	Component ¹	Source of variation					
			Repetition	df	Genotype ²	df	Isolate/Genotype	df
3+4	Aubusson	IE	<0.0001	2	0.8	1	0.1	14
		LP	0.001	2	<0.0001	1	<0.0001	14
		SP	0.03	2	0.9	1	<0.0001	14
3+4	Premio	IE	<0.0001	2	0.2	1	0.09	14
		LP	<0.0001	2	0.0006	1	0.001	14
		<u>SP</u>	0.002	2	0.8	1	<0.0001	14
3+4	Michigan	IE	<0.0001	2	1	1	0.6	14
		<u>LP</u>	0.008	2	<0.0001	1	0.2	14
		SP	<0.0001	2	0.1	1	<0.0001	14
5	Bermude	IE	0.0005	2	0.5	1	0.2	1
		LP	0.1	2	0.4	1	1	1
		SP	<0.0001	2	0.4	1	0.1	1
5	Expert	IE	0.0001	2	0.02	1	0.6	1
		LP	0.12	2	0.003	1	0.03	1
		SP	0.01	2	0.1	1	0.7	1
5	Sankara	IE	<0.0001	2	0.7	1	0.1	1
		LP	<0.0001	2	0.002	1	0.2	1
		SP	<0.0001	2	0.9	1	0.3	1

¹An underlined component means that the data did not follow a normal distribution required for the ANOVA, however a non-parametric test (Kruskal-Wallis) gave the same results.

²*p-values* in bold indicate a significant interaction effect between the repetition factor and the component.

Figure S1. (A) Infection efficiency (IE) as a %, (B) latency period (LP) in degree-days and (C) sporulation capacity (SP) in mg of spores/uredinia for the two *Puccinia triticina* genotypes 166 317 0-G1 and 166 317 0-G2 assessed on cultivars Apache and Michigan. Isolates were sampled from cv. Apache in 2012, 2014 and 2016. Within a box plot, the black diamond represents the mean value and the bar indicates the median. Letters indicate significant difference between genotypes, in Kruskal-Wallis tests (C) or ANOVA (A and B).

Figure S2. Infection efficiency as a %, latency period in degree-days and sporulation capacity in mg of spores/uredinia for *Puccinia triticina* genotypes of pathotype 106 314 0 measured on cultivars Apache and Michigan. Isolates were sampled from cv Apache, in 2005-2006, 2012-2013 and 2015-2016. Within a box plot, the black diamond represents the mean value and the bar represents the median value. Letters indicate significant differences between genotypes in Kruskal-Wallis tests (B and C) or ANOVA (A).